

TEACHERS' INSTRUCTIONAL CAPABILITY IN RELATION TO STUDENTS' EAGERNESS TO LEARN ENGLISH

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Abstract. This study explored the influence of teachers' instructional capability on the students' eagerness to learn English in public elementary schools. In this study, the researcher selected the 220 public elementary school students in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal as the respondents of the study. Stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. Non-experimental quantitative research design using descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected on the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation and multiple linear regression analysis. Findings revealed that teachers' instructional capability and students' eagerness to learn English in public elementary schools were described as extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated that there is a significant relationship between teachers' instructional capability and students' eagerness to learn English in public elementary schools. Evidently, regression analysis proved that teachers' instructional capability in terms of managing students' conduct and encouraging intellectual creativity were significant predictors of students' eagerness to learn English in public elementary schools in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal. In other words, teachers' instructional capability has influence on the process in students' eagerness to learn English in public elementary schools. The study, therefore, conducted for further utilization of findings through publication in reputable research journal.

KEY WORDS

1. Instructional capability.
2. Eagerness to learn
3. English language

1. Introduction

Many people have a strong desire to learn English for various reasons such as improving job prospects, traveling abroad, making foreign friends, and more. Due to the importance of English and the high demand for learning it, there are various formal and informal ways available for people to learn the language. However, not all learners find it easy to achieve their English learning goals and follow the language learning process effectively. It is crucial for students to know the appropriate strategies to facilitate their own learning.

Therefore, researching students' eagerness to learn English is an intriguing topic for researchers. This interest is driven by the researcher's previous observations, the significance of students' eagerness for successful language learning, and the inconsistent results of previous research. Recently, researchers have used the term "eagerness to learn English" to de-

scribe the extent to which students value English language learning outcomes and participate in academic and non-academic school activities. This definition typically includes a psychological component related to students' sense of belonging at school and their acceptance of school values, as well as a behavioral component related to their participation in school activities.

Eagerness to learn is seen as a tendency towards learning, working with others, and engaging in a social institution, as evidenced by students' sentiments that they belong at school and their involvement in school activities. Researchers are also exploring whether a lack of interest in learning during adolescence will have long-term implications. As mentioned by Francis et al. (2018), learners that are more willing to learn achieve more academically. Similar to this, Attard (2013) pointed out that keen learners engage in the lesson in meaningful ways by taking part in classroom activities, working together with teachers and students, and conducting their own learning reflections. Similarly, Ayub et al. (2016) concluded that eager students would seek out activities either within or outside the classroom that would lead them to be successful in their learning in science. Students who are more engaged in their studies will learn more, retain information, and store it in their brains than those who are not (Kim et al., 2015). Sadly, the study by Otoo et al. (2018) revealed that learners' eagerness to learn English has been dropping over time, which has caused issues for English teachers and school administrators around the world. For instance, according to a report by White (2015), the majority of students in schools around the world ignore classroom activities and the subject matter itself owing to a lack of interest and desire, which results in low academic accomplishment in many learning areas. Additionally, McGlynn and Kozlowski (2016) claimed that in a classroom where students lack eagerness to learn, misconceptions about fundamental ideas arise,

leading to students' difficulties in a variety of subjects and decreasing their interest in sticking with demanding and time-consuming activities. According to Prudente (2011), who focused on the Philippine context, the declining results of Filipino students on the National Achievement Test (NAT) are already evidence that there is an issue with the learners' eagerness to learn. On one hand, Hamzeh (2014) described teachers' instructional capability as a generalized plan for a lesson which includes structure, instructional objectives and an outline of planned tactics, necessary to implement the strategies. As explained by Saputra and Aziz (2014), the results of effective teaching, as described by educators and institution representatives, refer to learning outcomes that are durable, flexible, functional, meaningful, generalizable, and application-oriented. Raba (2017) also explained that the effective teaching strategies results in independent-learning, thinking, collaboration and regulation-skills. On the other hand, studies showed that there is a link between teachers' instructional capability and students' eagerness to learn. For instance, Wegner, Minnaert and Strehlke (2014) results revealed that learners become more active and engaged in the learning process and learn better when their teachers use different teaching strategies in the classroom. As pointed out by Khalid et al. (2013) instructional capability that teachers use in the classroom increases students' commitment to learning, and students always remember what they did, not what they memorized. Similarly, Ridwan, Sutresna and Haryeti (2019) made clear that to create an active classroom, teachers should use teaching strategies because when the class is active students will be active. The gap on the above-mentioned past studies is that most of it were conducted in foreign setting, and most of it was conducted before the pandemic and during the distant learning education set-up. Hence, utilizing a quantitative technique, the researcher would close the research

gap by carrying out a study in the Philippine context, namely in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal. Specifically, the researcher used descriptive correlational design to have a better understanding of the role of teachers' instructional capability as predictor of students' eagerness to learn English in selected elementary public schools which is found to be scarce. This study aimed to investigate the link between these characteristics that may serve as the basis for intervention programs and improve practices in the field of English education by surveying students in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis. The researcher used artificial intelligence tools to proofread this paper, specifically to improve its accuracy, coherence, and overall quality. This was done to maintain transparency and adhere to ethical standards in research. The use of AI for proofreading demonstrates a commitment to responsibly leveraging advanced technologies and acknowledges the increasing prevalence and capability of AI in academic and professional writing.

2.1. Research Design—The study utilized a non-experimental design using the descriptive correlation technique of research. This technique is designed to gather data, ideas, facts, and information related to the study. Quantitative research deals with numbers, logic, and an objective stance, focusing on numeric and unchanging data, detailed convergent reasoning, and the generation of a variety of ideas about a research problem (Babbie et al., 2010). According to Myers and Well (2013), correlated design examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause-and-effect relationships between variables. It enabled the researcher to observe two variables at a point in time and was useful in describing the relationship of the factors of both variables. Moreover, the study also looked into the relationship among two variables – teachers' instructional capability and students' eagerness to learn English in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal. The interest of the study is to investigate which among the domains of teachers' instructional capability significantly influences the students' eagerness to learn English in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study involved Grade 6 students in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal. A total of 220 respondents were selected using a stratified random sampling technique. This method divides the population into smaller sub-groups, or strata, based on shared attributes such as income or educational attainment. According to Shi (2015), stratified random sampling is appropriate when there is heterogeneity in a population that can be classified with ancillary information.

The inclusion criteria for selecting respondents were based on the ability to provide information relevant to the study's purpose. Only bonafide enrolled Grade 6 students with good moral character who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. The study was limited to the nature of the problem based on the research questions and did not consider the gender and socio-economic status of the students.

2.3. Research Instrument—The study employed the researcher-made questionnaires which were drafted to fit the context of the respondents of this study. The instrument was divided into two parts. The first part was about the Teachers' Instructional Capability, which is

distributed among the three indicators, namely managing students' conduct, encouraging intellectual creativity, and understanding students' individual capacity. The reliability of the original scale obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.976. In the manner of answering the question-

naire, the respondents made use the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of Teachers' Instructional Strategies, the researcher made use the range of means, description and interpretation as presented below:

Interpretation of Teachers' Instructional Capability

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The teachers' instructional capability is always observed.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The teachers' instructional capability is oftentimes observed.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teachers' instructional capability is sometimes observed.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The teachers' instructional capability is seldom observed.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The teachers' instructional capability is never observed.

Note. This table provides the interpretation of the teachers' instructional capability based on the range of mean scores.

The second part of the instrument was about students' eagerness to learn English. The instrument was composed of items that was divided into four parts which are self-activating, student engagement, learning emotions, and social commitment. The reliability of the original scale obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.85. In

the manner of answering the questionnaire, the respondents made use the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of students' eagerness to learn English, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

Interpretation of Students' Eagerness to Learn English

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The students' eagerness to learn English is always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The students' eagerness to learn English is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The students' eagerness to learn English is sometimes manifested.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The students' eagerness to learn English is seldom manifested.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The students' eagerness to learn English is never manifested.

Note. This table provides the interpretation of the students' eagerness to learn English based on the range of mean scores.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—Steps were undergone by the researcher in conducting the study after the validation of the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study.

The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao

City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the Schools Division Superintendent, and then to the school principals of the elementary public schools in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. The researcher proceeded to the distribution of the research instrument to the respondents after the approval to conduct the study. The study was conducted last November 9-10, 2023. Upon the distribution of the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and

explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the administration of the questionnaire, the study was done in the second quarter of school year 2023-2024. More so, the respondents of the study were given enough testing time for the questionnaires to be finished. After which, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the data retrieval of the questionnaire, the scores of each respondent were tallied to organize the data per indicator. After which, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the teachers' instructional capability and students' eagerness to learn English in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal. This was used to supply the answer for objectives 1 and 2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It was used in this study to assess the significant relationship between independent (teachers' instructional capability),

and dependent (students' eagerness to learn English) variables. It is a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it is usually denoted by r . This was used to supply the answer for objective 3. Multiple Linear Regression. It was applied to evaluate which domains of teachers' instructional capability significantly influence the students' eagerness to learn English in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal. This was used to supply the answer for objective 4.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the objectives of the study, as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extents of teachers' instructional capability and students' eagerness to learn English in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal; the significant relationship between teachers' instructional capability and students' eagerness to learn English in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal; and the domains of teachers' instructional capability significantly influence the students' eagerness to learn English in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal.

instructional capability in relation to students' eagerness to learn English of public elementary school teachers in Babak District in Island Garden City of Samal. It shows that the overall mean of instructional capability of teachers is 3.71 which is described as extensive. It means that the teachers' instructional capability is oftentimes observed. More so, managing students' conduct acquired the highest mean score of 3.91, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed by the grade 6 students, while understanding students' individual capacity got the lowest mean score of 3.59, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed by the respondents.

Table 1 shows the summary on the teachers' www.nijse.net

Table 1. Summary on Teachers’ Instructional Capability of Public Elementary School Teachers in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Managing Students’ Conduct	3.91	Extensive
Encouraging Intellectual Creativity	3.62	Extensive
Understanding Students’ Individual Capacity	3.59	Extensive
Overall	3.71	Extensive

The extensive rating on teachers’ instructional capability of grade 6 students means that the generalized plan for a lesson, which includes structure, instructional objectives, and an outline of planned tactics necessary to implement the strategies, is oftentimes observed in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal. This result is congruent to Saputra and Aziz’s (2014) results that effective teaching was de-

scribed by educators and institution representatives refer to learning outcomes that are durable, flexible, functional, meaningful, generalizable and application-oriented. More so, this result is in agreement with the idea of Temli- Dumus (2016) that teachers’ instructional capability is that teacher having the ability to use strategy that attract students’ attention and keep them on tasks.

Table 2. Summary on Students’ Eagerness to Learn English in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Self-Activating	3.33	Moderately Extensive
Student Engagement	3.48	Extensive
Learning Emotions	3.66	Extensive
Social Commitment	3.49	Extensive
Overall	3.49	Extensive

In Table 2 is the summary of the extent of students’ eagerness to learn English in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal as shown in the table obtained an overall mean score of 3.49 with a descriptive rating of extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested by the respondents. Adding more, results in Table 9 show that students’ eagerness to learn English in terms of learning emotions acquired the highest mean score of 3.66 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested, while, students’ eagerness to learn English in terms of self-activating acquired the lowest mean score

of 3.33 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested in Babak District in Island Garden City of Samal. The results of the analysis of the relationship between teachers’ instructional capability and students’ eagerness to learn English in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal, are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson product-moment correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 10 shows that teachers’ instructional capability has a significant positive relationship with the students’ eagerness to

learn English in Babak District in Island Garden City of Samal with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .486, p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of the teachers' instructional capability changes, students' eagerness to learn English in Babak District in Island Garden City of Samal also significantly changes. Adding more, the result indicates that teachers' instructional capability in terms of managing students' conduct, encouraging intellectual creativity, and understanding

students' individual capacity significantly correlated with students' eagerness to learn English in Babak District in Island Garden City of Samal with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) and coefficient correlation values of 0.567, 0.679, and 0.434, respectively. This led to the rejection of null hypothesis of no significant relationship between teachers' instructional capability and students' eagerness to learn English in Babak District in Island Garden City of Samal.

Table 3. Relationship Between Teachers' Instructional Capability and Students' Eagerness to Learn English in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal

Teachers' Instructional Capability	r-value	p-value	Decision
Managing Students' Conduct	0.567*	0.000	Reject H0
Encouraging Intellectual Creativity	0.679*	0.000	Reject H0
Understanding Students' Individual Capacity	0.434*	0.000	Reject H0
Over-all Teachers' Instructional Capability	0.486*	0.000	Reject H0

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

The findings of the current study denote a significant relationship between teachers' instructional capability and students' eagerness to learn English in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal. The present finding conforms to the proposition of Zakaria and Iksan (2012) that effective strategies allow students to exchange resources, question each other's conclusions, and defend their own ideas, which requires students to use higher-ordered thinking. Effective teaching strategies also affords student an opportunity to practice communicating scientific ideas. Effective teaching strategies benefit students in multiple ways, resulting in more meaningful learning connections. According to Raba (2017), effective teaching strategies results in independent- learning, thinking, collaboration and regulation-skills. Hence, in order to be able to reach the said results, new kinds of teaching processes are needed: active, constructive, goal-directed, diagnostic, reflective, discovery ori-

ented, contextual, problem oriented, case based, among others.

The significance on the influence of teachers' instructional capability on the students' eagerness to learn English in Babak District in Island Garden City of Samal was analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis. The Table 11 shows that when teachers' instructional capability in terms of managing students' conduct, encouraging intellectual creativity, and understanding students' individual capacity are considered as predictors of students' eagerness to learn English, the model is significant as evident on F-value of 13.159 with $p < 0.05$. It is therefore stated that teachers' instructional capability predicts the students' eagerness to learn English in Babak District in Island Garden City of Samal. Meanwhile, the computed adjusted R2 value of 0.268 indicates that teachers' instructional capability has contributed

English in Babak District in Island Garden City of Samal by 26.80. In addition, table shows that there are domains of teachers' instructional capability that significantly influence the students' eagerness to learn English in Babak District in Island Garden City of Samal. This table also indicates that only managing students' conduct and encouraging intellectual creativity are significant when the predictors are considered.

This means that the extent of students' eagerness to learn English increases by 0.330, and 0.152 for each unit increase in teachers' instructional capability. Thus, this leads to the rejection of null hypothesis that none of the domains of teachers' instructional capability that significantly influence the students' eagerness to learn English in Babak District in Island Garden City of Samal.

Table 6. Influence of Teachers' Instructional Capability on the Students' Eagerness to Learn English in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal

Teachers' Instructional Capability	Students' Eagerness to Learn English	B	Beta	S.E	p-value	Decisions
Managing Conduct	Students'	0.330*	0.254	0.089	0.000	Reject H0
Encouraging Intellectual Creativity	Intellectual	0.152*	0.144	0.069	0.000	Reject H0
Understanding Students' Capacity	Students' Individual	-0.036	0.028	0.071	0.085	Accept H0
R²			0.268			
F-value			13.159*			
p-value			0.000			

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

Affirming that students' eagerness to learn English is a function of teachers' instructional capability. This is in consonance with the Kearsley and Schneiderman (1999) Engagement Theory that students must be actively involved in their education through tactics that promote useful interpersonal engagement. Students are encouraged to pay close attention and participate in conversations, and they tend to depend more on their own intuition when an approach in the classroom is helpful for learning and allows students to explore and acquire scientific information.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the conclusion and recommendation of the researcher. The discussion is supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusion is in accordance with statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate which domains of teachers' instructional capability significantly influence the students' eagerness to learn English in public elementary schools utilizing non-experimental quantitative design using descriptive-correlation technique. The researcher selected the 220 elementary school students in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal as the respondents through stratified random sampling method. The researcher made use of modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires which was pilot tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. The extent of teachers' instructional capability of the public elementary school students in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal got an overall mean of 3.71 with an extensive descriptive rating. Also, teachers' instructional capability in terms of managing students' conduct, encouraging intellectual creativity, and understanding students' individual capacity obtained the mean scores of 3.91, 3.62, and 3.59, respectively. The extent of students' eagerness to learn English in public elementary school students in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal has an overall mean of 3.49 with an extensive descriptive rating. Also, of students' eagerness to learn English in public elementary school in terms of self-activating, student engagement, learning emotions, and social commitment obtained the mean scores of 3.33, 3.48, 3.66, and 3.49 respectively. The result showed that teachers' instructional capability has a significant positive relationship with the students' eagerness to learn English in public elementary school students in Babak District in Island Garden City of Samal with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .486, p < 0.05$). Likewise, teachers' instructional capability in terms of managing students' conduct, encouraging intellectual creativity, and understanding students' individual capacity have significant positive relationship with the students' eagerness to learn English in public elementary school students in Babak District in Island Garden City of Samal with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) with coefficient correlation values of 0.567, 0.679, and 0.434, respectively. The extent of teachers' instructional capability in terms of managing students' conduct and encouraging intellectual creativity significantly influenced students' eagerness to learn English in public elementary schools in Babak District in Island Garden City of Samal as evident on the F-value of 13.159 and $p < 0.05$. The r^2 value of 0.268 indicated that teachers' instructional capability has contributed significantly to the variability of students' eagerness to learn English in public elementary schools in Babak District in Island Garden City of Samal by 26.80

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated: Teachers' instructional capability in public elementary schools in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal was extensive. Meanwhile, teachers' instructional capability in public elementary school in terms of managing students' conduct, encouraging intellectual creativity, and understanding students' individual capacity obtained extensive descriptive rating. This means that the generalized plan for a lesson, which includes structure, instructional objectives, and an outline of planned tactics necessary to implement the strategies, is oftentimes observed. Students' eagerness to learn English in public elementary school in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal was rated as extensive. Students' eagerness to learn English in public elementary school in terms of student engagement, learning emotions, and social commitment acquired extensive ratings, while, students' eagerness to learn English in public elementary school in terms of self-activating belongs to moderately extensive rating. The result indicates that students' dedication to un-

derstanding the scientific material, as well as their participation in the classroom's English activities, is oftentimes manifested. The result showed that teachers' instructional capability has a significant positive relationship with the students' eagerness to learn English in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal. This means that as the extent of the teachers' instructional capability changes, students' eagerness to learn English in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal also significantly changes. The extent of teachers' instructional capability in terms of managing students' conduct and encouraging intellectual creativity significantly influenced the students' eagerness to learn English in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal. This affirmed that students' eagerness to learn English is a function of teachers' instructional capability in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the findings and conclusions generated from the study, the researcher recommends the following: Department of Education and policy makers should devise measures that may improve instructional capability to reverse and minimize, if not eliminate, a lack of eagerness to learn English. This could help determine those stu-

dents who have high potentials in English and to serve them accordingly. A school-based program for enhancing the eagerness to learn English among students through extensive training of learning strategies for students may be implemented. This program may be facilitated by different stakeholders such as teachers, community leaders, and parents, since it was found that parental support is a significant mediator on the relationship between teacher's pedagogical strategies and learning motivation. Moreover, teachers should use utilize effective pedagogical strategy which could serve as an intervention as well as a preventative measure for possible undesirable consequences of poor students' learning conditions. In addition, the study found that teachers' instructional capability only contributed to 26.80 percent of the total variability of students' eagerness to learn English in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal, thus, the researcher recommends that other researchers should conduct an explanatory study on the mediating factors that causes the relationship between teachers' instructional capability and students' eagerness to learn English in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal in a larger context should be conducted.

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